

Syntheses and spectral studies of mixed valence tetranuclear Cu^{II}/Cu^I complexes

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Abstract : A series of new mixed valence tetranuclear copper(II)-copper(I) complexes obtained from the reaction of Cu^IX (X = Cl, SCN, I) with [(Paa)Cu₂Cl₄] in acetonitrile. The Cu^IX and [(Paa)Cu₂Cl₄] are attached via two bridging chlorine atoms and the resulting complex has distorted trigonal planer geometry. CV, UV-vis and ESR spectroscopic studies established the presence of significant perturbation of the Cu^IX unit to the electronic structure of the copper(II) ion in [(Paa)Cu₂Cl₄].

Keywords : Mixed valence complex, copper(II)-copper(I) complexes, tetranuclear complex.

In continuation of our previous works on mixed valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes¹, in this paper we describe the synthesis and characterization of a series of mixed-valence Cu^{II}-Cu^I complexes X-Cu^I (Cl₂Cu^{II}paaCu^{II}Cl₂) Cu^I-X, where X⁻ = Cl⁻, SCN⁻, I⁻ and Paa = pyridine-2-carbaldehyde azine, in order to systematically study of the factors that control the rate of intramolecular electron transfer in such complexes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of compounds : The three Cu^{II}-Cu^I complexes were prepared by first adding 2 mmol of CuCl₂ with 1 mmol Paa ligand in acetonitrile. The resulting dinuclear Cu^{II} complex was then reacted with a 2 mmol of cuprous salt. The sequential route of the synthesis may be given as :

All the above dinuclear copper(II) complex and mixed-valence tetranuclear copper(II)-copper(I) complexes were well supported by elemental, FAB mass analysis.

Magnetic properties : The magnetic moment of these complexes were collected at ambient temperature. The

observed magnetic moment value for dinuclear copper(II) complex (1.81 B.M.) is quite close to the value expected for copper(II) complexes without interaction. The magnetic moment values of the present mixed-valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes are 1.78 B.M., corresponding to one cupric centre per mole of complexes.

ESR spectra X-band ESR spectra of these complexes were recorded for polycrystalline state at room temperature (RT) and liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT). Some representative spectra are shown in Fig. 1. Basic spectral features at both temperatures are the same. The ESR spectral parameters derived from their respective spectra are given in Table 1. The ESR spectra of dinuclear copper(II) and mixed valence tetranuclear copper(II)-copper(I) complexes gave similar spectral features and have two peaks. ESR spectra of the copper(II) dinuclear complex is indicative of $S = 1/2$. No $\Delta M_s = \pm 2$ signal (half-field) is observed in either case. Three anisotropic of g values (g_x, g_y, g_z) are well resolved. The hyperfine structures from the spectral curves for both type of dinuclear copper(II) and mixed-valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes are not seen which could be caused by intermolecular exchange interaction.

Electronic spectra : The solution and solid UV-Vis spectra of the complexes were recorded and some representative spectra are shown in Fig. 2. The solution spec-

Table 1. Colour, magnetic moments, spectral data (ESR and UV-visible) of the present complexes

Complex	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	g_x/g_1	g_y	g_z/g_2	λ_{max} (nm)	
						Solid	Solution
$[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2]$ (1)	Dark brown	1.80	2.182	—	2.053	755	389 690 963
$[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2(\text{CuCl})_2]$ (2)	Brown	1.78	2.2355	2.1334	2.019	770	404 671
$[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2(\text{CuI})_2]$ (3)	Brown	1.78	2.2357	2.1340	2.022	690	413 678
$[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2(\text{CuSCN})_2]$ (4)	Brown	1.79	2.2354	2.1336	2.020	725	405

Fig. 1. X-band ESR spectra (RT) of the polycrystalline complexes (a) $[(\text{Paa})\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ and $[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2(\text{CuSCN})_2]$.

tra are similar to those of solid. In solution dinuclear copper(II) complexes has a maximum at 691 nm while mixed valence complexes has maxima in the range $670\text{--}675 \pm 1$ nm which are typical of $d \rightarrow d$ transitions and accounts for the color difference of these two type of complexes (the $\text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{Cu}$ charge transfer bands in these complexes appear at much higher energy level (< 415 nm) and do not overlap with $d\text{-}d$ transition bands). Dinuclear copper(II) complex also appear to have absorption in the near-infrared region which may also be related to the d electrons. The intervalence charge transfer

Fig. 2. UV-visible spectra (nujol mull) of (a) $[(\text{Paa})\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ and $[(\text{Paa})(\text{CuCl}_2)_2(\text{CuSCN})_2]$.

is not common among mixed valence copper complexes with a distinct class I environment. Although such bands were observed by Wang *et al.*² and Pandeya *et al.*³. The $d \rightarrow d$ and LMCT absorption difference of these two type of complexes could be then related to the $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}\text{X}$ moieties which could perturb the energy levels of the d -orbitals of the copper(II) centers.

Electrochemistry: The cyclic voltammograms for the dinuclear copper(II) complex and mixed valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes in DMF : water (3 : 2). The localized valencies are maintained in solution as can be observed in cyclic voltammogram. The cyclic voltammogram of dinuclear and mixed valent copper(II)-copper(I) complexes are identical in spectral features and have two oxidation peaks ($\sim E_{\text{pa1}} 70 \pm 20$ mV, $\sim E_{\text{pa2}} 530 \pm 60$ mV). Two well separated oxidation peak and one anodic peak ($\sim E_{\text{pc}} -575 \pm 50$ mV) are well defined in copper(II) dinuclear and mixed valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes. The cathodic as well as anodic shift were observed e.g. in 2nd oxidation peak $75\text{--}115 \pm 2$ mV. The sharp oxidation peaks during the reverse scan is tentatively attributed due to deposit of copper(0) on the electrode surface. The deposit of copper(0) on the electrode

surface can originate the typical features of a redissolution process on the reverse scan⁴. The trend of anodic shift is given as $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{Cl}) < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{Br}) < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{I}}(\text{I})$.

Conclusion :

In summary, three new mixed-valence copper(II)-copper(I) complexes have been synthesized and characterized. The addition of $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}\text{X}$ moiety to a complex $[(\text{Paa})\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ (1) causes some structural variation of the Cu^{II} portion and a dramatic change of the copper(II) ion's electronic structure. Both structural change and the *d* orbital interference of the Cu^{I} ion may be responsible for the change of the electronic structure of the Cu^{II} ion.

Experimental

All the chemicals were purchased from commercial sources, they were of A.R. grade and used as supplied.

Physical measurements :

FAB mass spectra : FAB (fast atom bombardment) mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 mass spectrometer using Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature (RT) with *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix.

Magnetic data were collected at room temperature on a Gouy balance using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. unit) as calibrant. The molar susceptibilities were corrected for the diamagnetism of the constituent atoms by using Pascal constants. Electron spin resonance (ESR) spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series ESR spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band of 100 kHz modulation frequency. Tetracyanoethylene was used as field marker ($g = 2.00277$).

The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in 100% dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) solution using Shimadzu UV-VIS 160 Spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of $[(\text{Paa})\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_4]$ (1) :

To an acetonitrile (25 ml) solution of Paa (1.05 g, 5.0 mmol), CuCl_2 (1.34 g, 10.0 mmol) was added and stirred

well at 25 °C for 1 h. A dark brown precipitate obtained was filtered off, washed a couple of times with MeCN, Et_2O and dried under *in vacuo*. Yield ~ 80% (Found : C, 30.10; H, 2.02; N, 11.56. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_4$ (1) : C, 30.07; H, 2.08; N, 11.69%). FAB Ms (*m/z*) : Obsd. (Calcd.) : 478 (478.88).

Synthesis of $[\text{CuCl-CuCl}_2\text{-Paa-CuCl}_2\text{-CuCl}]$ (2), $[\text{CuI-CuCl}_2\text{-Paa-CuCl}_2\text{-CuI}]$ (3) and $[\text{CuSCN-CuCl}_2\text{-Paa-CuCl}_2\text{-CuSCN}]$ (4) :

To a suspension of the complex (1) (0.478 g, 1.0 mmol) in MeCN (25 ml), an MeCN (10 ml) solution of the cuprous chloride (0.198 g, 2.0 mmol) was added with stirring and it was continued for 5 h at 25 °C. A light brown precipitate obtained was filtered off, washed a couple of times with MeCN, Et_2O and dried under *in vacuo*. Yield ~ 60% (Found : C, 21.20; H, 1.41; N, 8.29. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{Cu}_4\text{Cl}_6$ (2) : C, 21.27; H, 1.47; N, 8.27%). FAB Ms (*m/z*) : Obsd. (Calcd.) : 677 (676.86). Complex (3) and (4) were prepared in similar manner using corresponding cuprous salt in place of cuprous chloride. Yield ~ 60% (Found : C, 16.49; H, 1.19; N, 6.53. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{Cu}_4\text{Cl}_4\text{I}_2$ (3) : C, 16.74; H, 1.16; N, 6.51%). FAB Ms (*m/z*) : Obsd. (Calcd.) : 860 (859.76). (Found : C, 23.21; H, 1.33; N, 11.67. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_6\text{Cu}_4\text{Cl}_4\text{S}_2$ (4) : C, 23.26; H, 1.38; N, 11.63%). FAB Ms (*m/z*) : Obsd. (Calcd.) : 722 (722).

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